

Review: DHCH 2022 - Digital Humanities Methodologies

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Fig. 1. Istituto Svizzero, Rom

1 INTRODUCTION

For the second time, the interdisciplinary digital humanities event DH^{CH} brought together a variety of experts, in this year's edition focussing on digital practices and humanities methodologies. Algorithmic methods are increasingly applied to research projects in the field of humanities, which creates a rising demand to analyse and document these approaches properly.

The Istituto Svizzero in Rome hosted the intensive three-day workshop, during which the invited speakers reflected on their methodologies and discussed the implications for their research. After a warm welcome in the beautiful gardens of the Istituto Svizzero, the conference officially opened with an introduction by Peter Fornaro, presenting the associations and collaborations of the event.

Diving into the conference's theme of digital practices and methodologies, Lorenzo Cantoni, professor at the Faculty of Communication, Culture, and Society at USI, presented his framework called "ABCDE" (Access, Better, Connect, Disintermediate, Educate) based on his experience in heritage and tourism, emphasizing the importance of access and mediation in digital media. Particularly, Cantoni underlined enriching the visitor experience through digital means and

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storytelling, for example by incorporating individual memories of locals.

Concerned about similar issues, Tugce Karatas, PhD candidate at Torino University's Department of Computer Science, proposed a unified framework for digital curation to create engaging, interactive, and immersive exhibitions while also taking into account future digital technologies, archiving, and accessibility concerns. Using the BeArchaeo project, Karatas showed the support of a reflexive methodology through the digital curation model.

In regard to cultural heritage curation, PhD candidate Giacomo Alliata discussed his study on audiovisual data collections, which provide particular issues for archiving, curating, and accessibility. He proposed an innovative framework to explore these archives by employing immersive environments to reach an embodied understanding.

Max Frischknecht, a member of the *Participatory Knowledge Practices in Analogue and Digital Image Archives* (PIA) project, is likewise interested in motivating users to become active participants, and proposed a generative design approach for visualizations. This methodology was developed specifically for cultural data in the PIA Project and allows for a plurality of visual alternatives. As an observational and dynamic generative design technique, it avoids usual biases, allowing for a more critical interpretation of the data.

Julien Raemy, who is also working on the PIA project, introduced the actor-network theory, a constructivist approach defined primarily by Bruno Latour that allows the description of individual influences on each other, on the developed model, and thus on how this particular knowledge representation will impact the various stakeholders. Raemy's research blog chronicles data modelling through this ANT lense (<https://phd.julsraemy.ch/>).

Moving on to archival methodologies in research settings, experienced software developer Adrian Demleitner underlined the need of prototyping in a durable and stable manner, since these objects constitute key epistemological entities of study. He suggested that participative techniques cause prototypes to become more accessible, translatable, and reformable. Demleitner is part of the PIA project, where he explores these approaches.

Collecting, processing, and preserving vast volumes of data is also a main concern for Petra Vlad and Rebecca Rochat, who discuss the continuous digital transformations at the Swiss Film Archive, which strives to save all audiovisual material created in Switzerland. Their mass acquisition policy without aesthetical or formal criteria leads to a large stream of heterogenous data that needs to be managed. Due to a lack of financing and resources, many cultural heritage institutions face similar challenges. Vlad and Rochat manage this difficult situation well, adding new approaches, altering their procedures as needed, and collaborating with professionals.

Margherita Schellino and Immacolata Iaccarino discussed the construction and methodology of a digital library, using the *Biblioteca anatomica*, which is part of a 17th century Italian genre of literary anatomies. Their focus lies on digitizing and publishing the collection, then transcribing one text manually as a case study.

Moritz Mähr, in charge of research data management at Stadt.Geschichte.Basel, continues the discussion on sustainable data, specifically aiming to create publicly accessible research data, which entails first safeguarding and archiving data, then curating and enabling access to the public.

Mähr established a field report to allow critical perspectives on epistemological and methodological consequences, in which he demonstrates the need for more awareness among humanities researchers to view their drafts as data, and thus to be able to sustain and archive these documents.

Anna Janka's research purpose was to raise social awareness that writing gender consciously has not begun in today's culture, but can be traced back almost 200 years. In her master's thesis, she explored Swiss governmental protocols from 1848 until 1963 through two distant reading methods (POS-tagging, RegEx) and one manual annotation of data sections to analyse naming practices and gender-inclusivity. Despite the adoption of gender-inclusive naming practices, she observed that social hierarchies of the period are visible. The least technical approach (Reg Ex) yielded the most insight into her study, which is reminiscent of Adrian Demleitner's presentation, in which he stressed employing the weakest technology to solve a problem.

Jessica Pidoux, postdoc researcher in citizen science at CEE, Sciences Po Paris, presented her doctoral thesis, in which she applied qualitative and quantitative methods to examine online dating practices. By studying graphical user interfaces, developers, and users, she aimed to gain a deeper understanding of online dating phenomena. The deployed algorithms, as predicted, promote a heteronormative sense of beauty, accentuate stereotypes, and construct idealized personalities.

Tobias Hodel posed big picture questions, such as how to remain critical researchers, how accessibility of technology infrastructure generates disparities, and how datasets are inherently biased. He stated that artificial intelligence or deep learning algorithms acquire by default their creators' preconceptions, hence making decisions that the developers may not even be aware of. Lastly, Hodel introduced the CARE data principles, developed by the Indigenous Data Governance, that add ethical and historical context to the already existing FAIR data principles.

As a highlight of the conference, Willard McCarty, one of digital humanities' founding fathers, spoke on the relations between digital humanities and artificial intelligence. Elaborating the nuanced meanings of the terms *artificial* and *intelligence*, he emphasizes their potential, aiming to foster a conscientious awareness of how "worlds are made and unmade, in order to participate in the processes". He articulated the tension between fear and curiosity in the face of new technology, citing Openheimer, and the power of prophetic expectations of equally utopian and dystopian proportions.

The accompanying program of the conference contained the visit to the nearby located European Space Agency, where we received a warm welcome and a tour of their current exhibition. Subsequently, ESA's PhD candidates presented their research projects, which demonstrated a diverse range of applications for ESA's satellite data; detecting marine litter, gathering and labelling agricultural information, tracking and understanding dengue-fever outbreaks, forecasting weather, and improving edge and cloud computing in space within limited resources.

It became evident that the computational methods used to answer their research questions are very similar to the field of digital humanities and computer science in general. This provides a common foundation to discuss methodology, demonstrating the importance of data science and interdisciplinary projects.

In conclusion, the conference brought together a wide variety of approaches to address digital practices and methodologies, resulting in valuable insights and new perspectives to apply to ones own research. I am looking forward to hearing updates on all presented projects, maybe even at next year's edition of the conference.

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